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Optimized power grid operations for negative pricing using collective intelligence

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Abstract:

Electricity pricing in the market has been going negative in recent days due to lower demand or Net Demand Variability (NDV) in the instances of surplus supply due to variable additional sources in the market. The WG (Working Group) analysis reflects the same as fossil fuels like coal/gas are relieved by renewable energy like wind/solar. Negative pricing (NP) is a market-based methodology to administrate excess supply to electric grid as this excess supply imbalances the supply/demand curve. NP is predominant in western countries like Europe, Americas & Australia. But it is getting more common these days in Indian grid. Mere cutting off the source may help the administration manage the situation, but NP, if used with a Collective Intelligence (CI) can help both suppliers, users & the overall economy of the nation. Here CI refers to the data interaction among suppliers, users & power grid administrators with the aid of AI. CI here helps industries consuming power to get prepared in advance to use the available power or subsidized power to keep up the demand and avoid the grid operation in NP regime. The way of dealing with NP & utilizing a catastrophe as an opportunity is discussed in this paper.

CI has been implemented in many countries among various electricity suppliers, but not among the various users of industry. Observed energy savings ranging from 10~30% (\$220~\$1.7 billion) has been experienced by various countries. If CI is extended among these industrial stakeholders with effective planning and implementation mentioned in this article, the % savings could even exceed above 30% in energy and \$1.7 billion.

Keywords:

Net Demand Variability, Working Group, Collective Intelligence, Negative Pricing.

1. Introduction:

Electricity pricing fixed by the utilities, grid administrators have various components and the final price paid by the users is a collection of these components including tax levied by the respective governments. The pricing strategy is usually based on supply and demand in short- and long-term markets. Demand has a stronger hold on how to decide the final price. If demand falls, then the price of the produce must be brought down if it still wants to be in the market or it must quit to avoid a business deal that may end up in a loss.

Figure. 1: [23]: Wholesale electricity price

In the above fig wholesale electricity price when supply meets demand= \$200/30000 MW or \$0.0067/MW or 6.7 cents/KW.

Figure. 2: [25]: Market Clearing price

The above curve explains the Market clearing price (MCP) as an intersection point by two curves, the power supply curve, and the power demand curve. Various power sellers offering to sell power based on their production cost are mentioned and renewables hold the minimum price offer.

Negative Pricing (NP) was first reported in the German intraday market in 2007 and the German-Austrian day-ahead market in 2008. These reports started the new phenomena making the pricing of electricity in the market below zero, resulting in the suppliers paying the users to buy electricity. The price is below the market fixed price and the dynamic price (intraday) arising from the oversupply situation leads to this scenario. The negative value resulting in the loss to the supplier or the supplier paying the amount to the user to utilize the product (electricity) to stay in the market. If the supplier is not ready to pay the customer in this instance, he must quit the market and lose his opportunity to stay in the market. The supplier must work out a balance of costs incurred in exiting the market & make a reentry. The costs are the start & shut down of the electric generating units that require fuel and other resources. If the cost of start/shut down is more than the negative price for a period, then the supplier chooses to stay in negative pricing. If on the other hand, the cost of staying in negative pricing is more, then the power supplier exits the market.

Negative prices put a lot of stress on the power supplier's side as they are expected to bear losses in addition to making up competitive pricing made by renewables.

Figure. 3: [24]: Scenario of Negative Pricing (NP)

Scenario of NP usually occur during a long festival or the long weekends where the power demand is so low.

coal until the percentage of share of electricity was low. But after 2010 & 2015 the share of new tech as a supplier to grid has gone up as the capital required to start one is a fraction of the cost of nuclear/coal units.

New disruptive units can run with lesser profit margins for a longer span of time as they generate more revenue during normal grid hours and save the money for a NP scenario. The profit margin is high, and they can sustain more losses. Infrastructure requirement is very low compared to heavy industrial group of nuclear/coal.

Hydro unit's start-up of Hydro units is not an expensive process & renewables can easily be pulled-in/pulled-out of grid/market as & when required as they don't require unit ancillaries to start/shut down the unit.

When NP comes into picture nuclear & fossil fuels are the worst affected. They lose more revenue, a part of that is generated to save them from start/shut down costs.

2. Merit order dispatch:

The Merit order dispatch (MOD) is the mechanism used to administer the sequence used to start the units when there is a demand and stop the same when there is a low or poor demand.

Figure. 6: [20]: Merit Order Dispatch

Merit order dictates which or what kind of unit to be started and run based on fixed & variable costs involved in the cost of power generation. Fixed costs include salary of operating personnel, interest on the loan availed for the project etc. Variable costs include the cost of fuel, consumables etc. Higher variable cost will result in higher merit order dispatch meaning they are given least priority of request to join the electricity grid to supply power.

In the above fig-6 renewables (PV, wind) are preferred first to serve the grid with power as the price of electricity generated is low and the fuel requirement is nil & so does the order goes on high for power plants that requires expensive fuel to run for generating electricity. Base load units are usually nuclear and coal as their generation is almost constant over a period of time (say, a month) as the external environment of rain, cyclone doesn't affect them much unlike PV (depends on sunshine & may not perform well in a cloudy day or a week with bad weather) and wind (depends on seasonal weather for winds with reasonable wind velocity to achieve some decent output with intermittent interruptions that may destabilize the grid stability) as constant output from electricity sources don't disrupt the smooth operation of electricity grid.

Negative pricing becomes synonymous with grids with oversupply. NPs are implemented worldwide and are mentioned in the following table. The table below is regional to a particular geographic zone and based on regulations on their jurisdiction.

Table. 1: Worldwide Negative Pricing

Market	Offer floor
CAISO: California ISO (Independent system operator)	-\$150/MWh
ERCOT: Electric Reliability Council of Texas	-\$250/MWh
ISO-NE: ISO- Northeast	-\$150/MWh
MISO: Midcontinent ISO	-\$500/MWh
NYISO: New York ISO	-\$1000/MWh

PJM: Pennsylvania-New Jersey-Maryland Interconnection	No floor
IESO: Independent Electricity system operator, Ontario, Canada	-\$2000/MWh
AEMO: Australian Energy Market Operator	-\$1000/MWh

There is no ISO (Independent system operator) that offers “no limit for bidding price” as “Gate closure” (It is the time available for the market participants to submit their final offers and bids by automated bidding software).

From the above table it can be noted as ISOs with its maximum share of nuclear power, offers a relatively higher amount on offer floors as the impact of negative pricing over nuclear power is offset by Carbon credits, REC & cost involved in start/shut down of one such unit. E.g., MISO.

ISOs with the maximum share of renewables like solar, wind etc., offer a relatively much more amount on negative pricing as quick start/stop is possible. E.g., NYISO.

Merit order dispatch (MOD) dictates “Gate closure” sequence of power units dispatching power and these days’ tax credits, REC for renewables offset NP for a short period & ISO rule also allows the same.

Table. 2: India’s Negative Pricing

<i>Month</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>State</i>	<i>NP in negative rupees/kWh</i>
July	2020	Tamilnadu	-1
June	2021	Rajasthan	-0.5 to -1.5
April	2022	Gujarat	-3
May	2022	Andhra Pradesh	-0.5 to -2

The above-mentioned rates were paid by the power suppliers to stay on the grid for a period. For e.g., a power supplier must pay Rs 1* unit generated to the grid to stay online. There will not be any payment for electricity generated by the supplier in addition to NP.

NP occurrence is now forecasted using various models using Machine learning, Artificial Intelligence, Agent based models, stochastic programming & optimization models, but due to

limitations in these advanced models the occurrence of NP has made itself. Loss of revenue is the result of NP. NP can be made profitable to power suppliers who are under stress by simple methods. Renewables (RE) are enjoyed a lot as they are paid for the electricity, they are generated and in addition to REC's they can trade for money. Recent trends of declining prices of solar panels have motivated many communities and households to go for small and medium-sized installations to trade electricity with the grid operators listing them as suppliers. With more suppliers, the grid gets more renewable energy.

Renewable Energy Credits/ Certificates (REC) are credits given to renewable energy units for every 1-Megawatt hour of electricity, meaning 1 REC= 1 Megawatt hour of electricity generated by renewable energy.

The price of REC is available in the energy trading market of different countries and available on an intraday basis on respective websites.

For example, the price of 1 REC= Rs 360 for the month of February 2024 in Indian market.

Solar REC ranged from \$10 to \$ 400 for the year 2021 in the U.S market.

British Columbia Hydro is priced \$3/MWh in a long-term contract for 20 years in Canada.

On-spot price of \$48/MWh is fixed for Large-scale generation certificates (LGCs) in Australia for the 1st quarter of 2022.

Nuclear energy (NE) is baseload power plant that makes a lot of profit next to renewables. In addition to the electricity sold to grid they generate revenue from:

Production Tax credit (PTC) or Investment Tax credit: US energy policy act 2005 has enabled PTC of 1.8 cents/kWh for first eight years of operation.

Clean energy credits (CEC): Since NE is emission free it is eligible for CEC that can be traded in the market (some governments permit NE).

Carbon Pricing or Cap-and-Trade program: Regions with carbon pricing mechanisms allow NE to benefit with financial incentives or allowances.

Clean Energy Mandates: Regional jurisdictions empower NE to sell a percentage of power equivalent to RE or in the place of RE (if RE is not available at the time due to natural causes).

ZEC (Zero Emission Credits): It is not directly aimed at any specific price intended by the government. It mostly considers the technical aspect of hash rate.

Formula:

ZEC pricing=1+2+3

1=Estimating the US government's social cost of carbon (SCC). Is the metric used to denote the economic damages associated by the emission of additional tons of CO₂). \$51/metric ton CO₂ is US SCC, \$30/metric ton is OECD, \$85/metric ton CO₂ is as per Stern Review.

2=Subtract the portion of cost already captured in current wholesale power prices using RGGI (Regional Greenhouse Gas Initiative) carbon cap program. RGGI carbon cap program value is around \$13~\$14 per short ton of CO₂ allowances.

3=Converting values from \$/ton to \$/MWh (using New York system's carbon emissions per MWh). New York's overall electric system carbon emissions=0.2~0.3 metric tons CO₂/MWh (rate on 2021).

Apart from the above formula ZEC assigns value (that reflects environmental benefit) for calculating ZEC (region specific) include:

Market price differential, Carbon baseline & Power output of utility.

FFUs are baseloads, highly preferred for stable grid operation, units running on coal, lignite has other restrictions in running the unit as they produce air pollution due to the emissions out of their units. These emissions call for carbon tax. Carbon tax (CT) is the tax levied at a rate per every ton of Carbon Dioxide emitted to the atmosphere by the relevant entity or authority or organization.

The formula for calculating carbon tax:

CT= Emission factor*Heat rate*Operating hours*Capacity*Tax rate

Emission factor is the factor that denotes the tonnage of CO₂ emitted per ton of coal or lignite.

Heat rate is the efficiency of the unit (useful power output to the heat input) mentioned in heat unit Kilo Joule/ Kg or Btu/ kWh.

Operating hours are the total number of hours a unit runs in a year.

The capacity of the unit is the output electricity capacity of the unit.

Tax rate is the rate fixed by the regulatory authority to be paid by the entity for every ton of CO₂ emitted.

For e.g., a 100 MW unit with emission factor of 0.9 tons/CO₂ and a heat rate of 10000 Btu/kWh that runs for 6000 hours a year is fixed a tax rate of 3.413 Btu/kWh with \$30/ton CO₂ will have a carbon tax of

CT= \$5849400 or \$ 5.85 million a year.

This CT is additional cost is to be borne by FFU in addition to plant running costs that takes over a % of income or revenue generated by FFU. CT is levied in India and the rates are incrementing every year.

CI is a collaborative intelligence that includes the efforts and competitive capability of many individuals or contributors. The communication methodology is a combination of one-to-many, one-to-one and many-to one communication. Hardware and software are standardized among participants to ensure streaming, and exchange of data is live and real-time based.

CI in NP includes three-level forecasting networks to decentralize, strengthen networks, provides a reasonable value for any missing data (to execute and reach a consensus from the available data) in predicting exact periods of occurrence of NP and alert corresponding users or sources to be prepared to manage NP regime effectively.

Initiatives towards Collective Intelligence (CI) to administer NP is an emerging field and some milestones with examples towards managing are:

Equity Crowd Balancing Platform (Switzerland) aims in working effectively on the flexible loads with CI background by combining data from various participating distributed energy sources (DERs), optimizing the charging, or discharging patterns of electric vehicles, battery energy storage systems (BESS) and flexible loads. This platform is based on machine learning (ML) optimization algorithms considering user preferences, grid conditions and price signals.

EcoGrid EU project (Denmark) uses CI by using data from sources like smart meters, Res, consumer preferences with statistical approaches. This is a collaboration program by Siemens, IBM, Danish Energy Association, and households of Bornholm municipality. This project aimed in incentive programs to users to shift preferences of usage towards higher REs supply compared to FFUs. It also provided an effective solution for users to utilize more during NPs in the grid.

Piclo Flex (UK) is a platform and online marketplace trading platform for DERs and Distributed network operators (DNOs). CI is effectively utilized in this platform to incentivize users to utilize NP by adjusting consumption or generation patterns in a harmonized manner.

Brooklyn Microgrid (New York, USA) is a community-based project anchorages CI and blockchain technology allowing a peer-to-peer energy transaction among prosumers (producer and consumer) inside the microgrid. Excess Res is stored here among stakeholders in BESS or sold outside the microgrid. CI plays an important role in decision making process by analyzing various inputs from prosumers, stakeholders, energy storage providers and the microgrid operators.

Smart meters are available in the market with two-way communication capabilities e.g., Landis+Gyr Gridstream RF meter, Honeywell Elster REXUniversal meter, Sensus FlexNet Meter, Kamstrup OMNIA meter and Itron OpenWay CENTRON Meter including remote data collection, wireless data communication with billing and analysis. Various in-built capabilities such as real-time consumption monitoring, Time-of-use (TOU) & dynamic pricing, load disaggregation with profiling and very well integrated with automated load control systems. Transparency enabling options like consumer feedback and engagement with feedback mechanisms are imbibed with smart meters available providing insights and preferences using CI.

The above-mentioned programs are of small-scale or pilot programs that have been successfully tested or working can be implemented in a large-scale grid as the grid itself is a collection of various users and producers. Producers can be targeted to avoid oversupply to grid (as this destabilizes the grid) and bring forward the concept of NP. Demand side management is the topic that can balance NP to an extent by bringing various ideas mentioned below.

In general electricity grid pricing is based on the demand, when demand is high, the supplier has upper hand and he can dictate various conditions like maximum demand (MD), peak demand and impose restrictions on the users, but the exact opposite happens in a NP regime.

Fig.-7 [21] represents the Smart Grid that interconnects suppliers and users with communication interfaces and aided by AI for reasoning and analytics. AI here predicts or forecast a possible occurrence of NP, which is then communicated to users by two-way communication with users and AI capabilities of forecasting NP can alert the users using various communication technologies of RF or mobile SMS about an expected occurrence of NP can ask for a vote of willingness among

users to utilize an opportunity to improve production or operation goals of their individual organization.

Figure. 7: [21]: Smart Grid

3. Methods to manage NP:

3.1. Market pricing in NP situations:

During NP periods the MOD can be varied to make loss evenly among the suppliers keeping the bottom-line or base suppliers as thermal units and nuclear units. Here thermal units can be given the first preference to supply the grid and measures can be taken not to impose NP on thermal units as they already pay CT for the generation and the only income, they get is by the power generated and supplied to the grid. By not imposing NP to these units can boost their morale and be a stable unit to back-up the grid.

For e.g., a simple shutdown and a restart of a typical 250 MW thermal unit can consume around 60 to 65 kilo liters of furnace oil and the expenses mount up to Rs 30,00,000 (considering 1 litre of furnace oil=Rs 50) in addition to loss of generation for the starting period. CT is paid for this start-up, running and shutdown activity that takes a major portion of revenue. FFUs leverage the NP for a shutdown/re-start for a period and decide for further planning. Since NP occasions are predictable and not certain is a big backlog for these operations planning. Move towards reducing carbon is also challenged by the additional oil firing that may add more CO₂ to the environment.

Considering the loss FFUs face, they can be considered base units not affected by NP only during the NP period, but not during the normal grid condition, meaning NP MOD to be framed and normal MOD shall not be considered during NP regime.

NE can be considered above FFU in the newly framed NP MOD and can be charged with NP as NE gets revenue from PTC, CEC, carbon Pricing or Cap-and-Trade program and Clean Energy Mandates in addition to the electricity sold to the grid. Various credits and mandates can leverage the loss occurred due to operation in NP regime. It is seen that NE is not shut down due to NP as a re-start of NE plant usually cost more than \$30,000 to 75,000 depending on situations and time required to bring NE back to service.

REs can be considered on the top and NP can be implemented on all REs as they generate revenue from REC and free of CT. REC transactions can leverage their loss of revenue in NP. Moreover, the cost of building new REs like solar has come down as there is a steady decline in the cost of solar panels which makes the cost of spares cheap in the inventory and allowing them to operate in NP regime will not affect their working capital much as FFU or NE.

4. Stimulus programs for adaptive users:

4.1. Industries:

NP MOD using CI is a real-time platform that predicts an occurrence of NP and can do the following for the users in advance and give them time for preparation. Even though NP is utilized by users, this is only a small scale, but large-scale power consumers like industries can be also included in this NP MOD. Here NP MOD that can predict NP in advance, say before a day or week, for e.g., The Indian context of NP happens mostly during long public holidays. These holidays usually range from a day and may go up to three or four days. Low consumer demand is the prime reason for NP. Industries adapting NP MOD are informed prior to an occurrence of NP and during this condition, if any industry wishes to run in a public holiday can opt NP MOD and they can get electricity at subsidized rates for their operation. With lesser electric bills during a NP period some industries may opt for operation rather than declaring holiday. Legal provisions are to be made as employees working on a public holiday must be compensated accordingly. Reduced electricity bills can help in leveraging the compensation employees fairly.

The above-mentioned practice of employing people in public holidays is possible in a country like India as it is a country with diversified faiths. Public holidays are framed based on giving equal importance to every single faith in the country that is region or geographic specific. Other faith people not following the rituals by means of the faith but use the holiday for recreation. Some studies show people are ready to work these days if they are compensated fairly by their employers and these people do it voluntarily as they want to be economically independent. These people are mostly migrated workers or employees as it becomes not possible for them as they stay away from families and spending the holiday with family can be self-arranged later due to the travel of far-way places and long-journeys.

People or employees not interested in spending public holidays can be employed to run the industries to produce a desired amount of production with lesser expenses like subsidized electricity bills. This could be implemented on a pilot basis that confirms regulations imposed by competent authorities.

Table. 3: Industrial energy savings in NP regime

Serial no	Industry type	% Energy savings reduced consumption)	% change in energy bills (reduced bill)
1	Hydrogen hydrolyser	30~50	40~60
2	Data centers	20~30	20~40
3	Water treatment plant	15~25	15~30
4	Electric vehicle charging	10~20	10~25
5	Industrial process (like steel, cement)	5~15	5~20
6	Refrigeration & cooling	5~10	5~15
7	Pumping and water distribution	5~10	5~15
8	Compressed air systems	2~5	2~10

4.2. H2 electrolyzes:

Green H2 (GH2) is the fuel industry trend as the emissions from engines using H2 for combustion emit zero carbon. GH2 is obtained from electrolyzing water and different types of electrolyzes (electrolyzes split water into H2 and O2 using electrolysis) are available. Electricity power is used

to run these GH2 units, and they account for around 60%~80% of the total cost of production. When a NP is predicted, the GH2 units can be informed earlier to go for full production scale as there will electricity available in the grid at a subsidized price (this difference is collected from RE as they have the benefit of trading REC in energy market).

For e.g., Cost of H2 from electrolysis= \$3 to \$7 per kg. Here 80% is the cost of electricity utilized. I.e., $\$7 \times 0.8 = \$ 5.6$ per kg.

Table. 4: % Energy savings by various hydrogen electrolysis in NP regime

Serial no	Hydrogen hydrolyser	% Energy savings (reduced consumption)	% change in energy bills (reduced bill)
1	Alkaline electrolysis	50~70	60~80
2	Proton Exchange membrane	45~65	55~75
3	Solid oxide electrolysis	40~60	50~70
4	Anion exchange membrane	40~60	50~70
5	Polymer electrolyte membrane	35~55	45~65
6	Hydrogen production via Ammonia Cracking	30~50	40~60
7	Hi-pressure electrolysis	25~45	35~55

Recent innovations to blend existing auto fuels or household fuels e.g., GAIL has successfully blended PNG (piped natural gas) in Gujarat up to 8% by volume with H2 and blended PNG is safe like unblended PNG and can be used for household cooking without any additional equipment to carefully handle H2 (H2 being lighter requires special equipment to handle and be used as fuel). The potential of blending up to 20% is identified but requires modification in burners and ignition system. Price hike of PNG up to 20% is observed due to early adopters & will decrease in the mature stage due to adoption in economies of scale.

The same blending can be used for CNG (compressed natural gas) as HCNG or H2CNG (Hydrogen CNG) and a typical blending of 14 to 28% H2 with CNG for Light vehicles and 8 to 18% for heavy vehicles. H15 (15%Hydrogen) is a common HCNG blending available.

Blended or HCNG (normal 14 to 28%) costs 10 to 20% more than unblended CNG, For e.g., CNG price in India= Rs 85/kg. HCNG will be 10 to 20% expensive, but the mileage also increases up

to 10% on average. The advantages are leveraged by CTs nullify the % of blended H2 in HCNG. The % of CT in the total price of CNG accounts for 5 to 18%. In India there is no CT at present for CNG, but there are plans by the government to implement one.

Blended LPG is also priced 15 to 20 % more than unblended LPG, but the decreased emissions and 15% additional mileage are the points to consider bringing down carbon emissions.

During public holidays people commute for personal reasons & vehicles of Internal Combustion (ICE) engines make a lot of carbon emissions. During NP ramping up H2 with subsidized electricity can bring down the cost of H2 blended in fuels. All the above is possible only by Green H2 and not by Grey or Brown H2 as the H2 generation process involves fossil fuels. Subsidized power surely reduces the cost of H2 production in the NP regime.

CI here informs an occurrence of NP ahead of days and H2 production units can plan manpower and equipment availability and utilize the power generated to the grid. Large scale H2 units can even stop the occurrence of NP if operated in GW capacity region wise. With less or no chances of NP, existing power producers can operate their businesses can operate confidently for profit without the fear of loss.

Above mentioned CI models can be used to other industries keen in utilizing subsidized power to earn some profit in business and can stop occurrence of NP that stops the electricity generation units using nature given resources of sunlight and wind.

BESS storage charging in NP times is another model that is still present and active in some regions worldwide. Here, during the peak load periods BESS discharges stored energy from batteries to run home load and again gets the battery recharged when there is more available of RE in the grid. CI is more used, and devices communicate among themselves to achieve one. CI can also be used to program BESS discharging/recharging cycle during peak load period/NP regime.

Table. 5: % Energy savings by various BESS charging in normal grid condition and NP regime

Serial no	BESS type	% Energy savings in normal grid condition	% Energy savings in NP regime
1	Lead acid	5~15	20~40
2	Lithium ion	10~25	30~50
3	Flow batteries	15~30	40~60

4	Sodium ion	20~35	50~70
5	Zinc-iron flow	25~40	60~80

5. Conclusion and future enhancement:

The above-mentioned methods, when followed, can bring down the negative impacts of NP over the grid and the power operators thereby optimizing and making even the pay flow to all the suppliers and bring down losses. Recently a trend of power producing opting for “going out of business” is observed. This trend is dangerous as most of them are base load FFU affected by a non-linear supplier of RE. European Union countries faced this sort of power crisis during the recent “Ukraine War” as the power suppliers (FFUs) cannot come back to business due to short of funds and other resources even when there was a chance for them to bounce back in business. “Policy push” towards carbon free environment forced FFUs to close or demolish facilities without any available back-up plans made FFUs, the stable base load operators to quit the grid and business. Until a stable source of power like FFUs is established by technology, it is not good to make policy decisions by policy makers to rush for opting some new fad and worry later when there is no back-up plan for the dealing a crisis like “power crisis” recently experienced by the European Union member states.

The primal aim of optimization is to reduce the negative impact of NP on all power generation business and to keep the business alive and avoid the situation of power producers for “Going out of Business”.

Dealing with NP by cutting down the sources is not a wise method, but making use of this crisis an opportunity requires wise methods and novel ideas. Sourcing the excess power to needy users can be made in advance and give them a chance to make and prepare to use this occasion as an opportunity to develop their business and achieve their goals with a win-win complement.

The savings % mentioned in the tables [3], [4], [5] are individually observed by operating industries, hydrogen hydrolysers without any CI and they are independent. CI can bridge these gaps by predictive algorithms that will also automatically communicate various stakeholders about a possible occurrence of this NP regime & help pre-plan users accordingly, thereby avoiding various grid suppliers (Gas, Oil, Thermal, renewable etc.) and be ready to operate in a situation

where there is an occurrence of NP followed immediately by a major load or power withdrawal by users that can affect the smooth operation of grid. Even NP can be totally avoided by CI. CI along with existing hardware can manage NP very well.

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